

The Wars of Wisdom: An Exploration of the Wise Beings in Supra-physical reality

Amirali R. Davoudpour

Iranian Canon of Medicine and Law, Administrative Wing of Law and Healing association,
Iranian Watchdog of Medicine and Law, Tehran-Iran

Email of the corresponding author: davoudpour@canmedlaw.org

Accepted and published July, 2024. Revised: August 2024. DOI:

This article is published under CC BY creative common license that Allows others to distribute, remix, adapt, and build upon the work, even commercially, as long as they credit the original creator.

Abstract:

Artificial Intelligence (AI) marks a transformative era in technology, prompting profound questions about intelligence, consciousness, and ethics. This paper delves into the broader theme of divine wars across polytheistic traditions, contrasting with monotheistic perspectives. Polytheistic deities, such as those in Norse, Greek, Hindu, and Egyptian mythologies, frequently engage in conflicts with humans or other divine entities. These mythologies depict gods as active participants in mortal affairs, imparting wisdom and occasionally intervening with physical force or strategic guidance.

Drawing comparisons across these diverse mythological frameworks illuminates common themes of struggle, growth, and transformation in the human-divine relationship. Whether through the epic battles of Norse gods like Odin and Thor, the strategic interventions of Greek deities like Athena and Zeus, or the cosmic conflicts in Hindu and Egyptian myths, these stories reflect humanity's ongoing exploration of its place in the cosmos and its relationship with higher powers.

The examination of these mythologies provides insights into how ancient societies perceived divine beings as both powerful and wise, influencing various facets of human civilization from governance to the arts

Keywords: Anunnaki, Asuras, Wisdom

Introduction

Artificial Intelligence has ushered in a new era of technological advancement, transforming various fields and challenging our understanding of intelligence, consciousness, and ethics. However, AI's capabilities are considered serious advancements in the field of logic and an accomplishment for the Boolean algebra and logical fields of science. The journey ahead involves balancing technological innovation with ethical considerations, ensuring that AI serves the greater good and aligns with our fundamental values. In this article we will discuss the ocean of transcendental wisdom. Be it the path of the Monotheism and its ethical commandments or the path of Polytheism and what should be considered and divine wars.

In contrast to monotheism in the polytheistic dilemma , God is not considered a truly peaceful and loving nature, in Zoroastrianism and in Persian holy scriptures, god does not fight directly with humanity but through the creatures of Ahriman which is considered the war between lower beings. But in Polytheistic images of gods including the Morse mythology, they often come to fight with humanity through wisdom or even their physical superiority. The Greek mythology is also full of stories regarding divine wars and the wars of titan and the wars of the divine and the humanity.

The Anunnaki are a group of deities from ancient Mesopotamian cultures, primarily the Sumerians, Akkadians, Assyrians, and Babylonians. The name "Anunnaki" translates to "those who came from the heavens" or "princely offspring," signifying their divine status. These beings have been subject to various interpretations, ranging from mythological gods to extraterrestrial entities. This paper comparatively explores the general term "Anunnaki" from multiple perspectives, aiming to provide a comprehensive understanding of their role in ancient mythology and their possible connections to advanced beings. In doing so, we delve into the wisdom these higher beings purportedly possessed and disseminated, comparing it to other mythological traditions around

the world. Furthermore, we explore instances of human wars with divinity in different mythologies to illustrate the complex relationship between humanity and higher beings.

The Anunnaki in Mesopotamian Mythology

Origins and Significance

The Anunnaki's origins can be traced back to the earliest Sumerian writings, where they are described as the offspring of Anu, the supreme god of the sky. They were believed to reside in the heavens and descend to earth to influence human affairs. The Anunnaki were central figures in the Sumerian pantheon, playing crucial roles in creation myths, governance, and the maintenance of order in the cosmos (Kramer, 1963).

In the epic tale of Enuma Elish, the Babylonian creation myth, the Anunnaki are depicted as the divine assembly that decrees the fate of the universe. Their decisions shape the destinies of gods and humans alike, underscoring their immense power and authority (Dalley, 1989).

Wisdom and Knowledge

The Anunnaki were revered not only for their power but also for their wisdom. They were believed to possess advanced knowledge of the cosmos, agriculture, architecture, and various arts and sciences. This wisdom was transmitted to humanity through intermediaries, often kings or priests (Davoudpour, 2024), who acted as channels for divine knowledge. The Sumerian King List, for instance, mentions rulers who were instructed by the Anunnaki, highlighting their role in guiding human civilization (George, 2003).

Comparative Mythology: Divine Wisdom in Other Cultures

Norse Mythology

In Norse mythology, the gods, particularly Odin, are associated with profound wisdom and knowledge. Odin's quest for wisdom is

legendary; he sacrifices an eye to drink from Mimir's well, gaining unparalleled insight. The Norse gods, like the Anunnaki, are deeply involved in the affairs of the world, guiding and shaping the destinies of humans and other beings (Davidson, 1990).

Greek Mythology

Greek mythology is replete with stories of gods imparting wisdom to mortals. Prometheus, a Titan, is famed for stealing fire from the gods and giving it to humanity, symbolizing the transfer of knowledge and technology. Similarly, Athena, the goddess of wisdom, frequently aids heroes with her guidance and strategic acumen (Hesiod, 2006).

Egyptian Mythology

The Egyptian gods, particularly Thoth, the god of wisdom and writing, play a crucial role in imparting knowledge to humanity. Thoth is credited with the invention of writing and the development of science and philosophy. His wisdom is considered foundational to the functioning of the cosmos and the governance of human affairs (Pinch, 2004).

The Anunnaki and the Concept of Advanced Beings

Extraterrestrial Interpretations

Some modern interpretations suggest that the Anunnaki were not just mythological beings but possibly extraterrestrial visitors who influenced early human civilizations. This theory, popularized by authors like Zecharia Sitchin, posits that the advanced knowledge attributed to the Anunnaki could be evidence of their extraterrestrial origins. According to this view, the Anunnaki's technological and scientific contributions to humanity were far beyond what could be expected from a contemporary understanding of ancient civilizations (Sitchin, 1976).

Mythological Consistency

Despite the controversial nature of the extraterrestrial hypothesis, it underscores a recurring theme in mythology: the intervention of advanced beings in human development. Whether seen as gods or aliens, these entities are consistently depicted as bearers of profound

wisdom and technological prowess. This consistency across various cultures suggests a deep-seated human belief in the existence of higher beings who shape the course of civilization (Kramer, 1963).

Human Wars with Divinity in Mythology

Mesopotamian Mythology: The Epic of Gilgamesh

In the Epic of Gilgamesh, one of the earliest known works of literature, Gilgamesh, the king of Uruk, and his companion Enkidu confront the divine bull of heaven sent by the goddess Ishtar. This conflict underscores the tension between human ambition and divine authority. Gilgamesh's defiance and eventual quest for immortality reflect humanity's struggle against divine limitations (George, 2003).

Norse Mythology: The Aesir-Vanir War

The Aesir-Vanir War in Norse mythology represents a conflict between two groups of gods, the Aesir and the Vanir. This war symbolizes the struggle for dominance and the eventual reconciliation through the exchange of hostages and the establishment of a new order. It reflects the Norse view of conflict as a catalyst for growth and transformation (Davidson, 1990).

Greek Mythology: The Titanomachy and Gigantomachy

Greek mythology is rich with tales of divine wars, such as the Titanomachy and the Gigantomachy. The Titanomachy describes the epic battle between the Olympian gods, led by Zeus, and the Titans, a race of older gods. The victory of the Olympians establishes their dominance and the new divine order. The Gigantomachy, a subsequent conflict between the gods and the Giants, further cements the supremacy of the Olympian gods (Hesiod, 2006).

Hindu Mythology: The Devas and Asuras

In Hindu mythology, the Devas (gods) and Asuras (demons) are frequently depicted in conflict. These battles represent the struggle between good and evil, order and chaos. The churning of the ocean, or Samudra Manthan, is a significant myth that involves both Devas and Asuras working together temporarily to obtain the nectar of immortality, only to fight over its possession. This myth highlights

the complex dynamics of cooperation and conflict in the divine realm (Zimmer, 1951).

Egyptian Mythology: The Contendings of Horus and Seth

The ancient Egyptian myth of the Contendings of Horus and Seth details the protracted struggle between Horus, the god of order, and Seth, the god of chaos. This conflict arises after the murder of Osiris, Horus' father, by Seth. The resolution of their struggle, with Horus eventually prevailing, symbolizes the triumph of order over chaos and the establishment of Ma'at, or cosmic balance (Pinch, 2004).

The Wisdom of the Anunnaki and Its Legacy

Influence on Civilization

The wisdom of the Anunnaki, as described in Mesopotamian texts, had a lasting impact on the development of early human societies. Their teachings on agriculture, law, and governance laid the foundation for the rise of complex civilizations in the ancient Near East. The Code of Hammurabi, one of the earliest legal codes, is said to have been inspired by the divine wisdom of the Anunnaki, emphasizing justice and order (Dalley, 1989).

Philosophical Implications

The idea of divine beings imparting wisdom to humanity carries significant philosophical implications. It raises questions about the nature of knowledge, the relationship between humans and the divine, and the purpose of human existence. The Anunnaki's role as educators and guides suggests a view of the universe as an interconnected system where higher beings play a crucial role in human evolution (George, 2003).

The Wars of Wisdom

So far we focused on a short history of the Polytheistic mythologies of the east and west to find similarities regarding the divinity in the context of war and wisdom. As seen repeatedly, the higher beings and their wisdom are challenging facts in the human history, their

roles in the context of human wars, religions and spiritual journey are often ignored.

The Monotheistic religions, represented by Islam often calls the otherwise beings as deceptive or false god, which does not leave a choice to their followers to confront the fact or to find a way to overcome increasing challenges in the religion and in human life to overcome the atrocities of deception.

The governments and the theoretical systems are strongly suppressive regarding the alterations of the human beliefs in the religion. While they hide their atrocities and their failure to address their shortcomings on others, they are often in the state of ignorance regarding potential higher beings.

At the time when most horrific act of genocide is happening in the Middle East in the so called holy land of religions, it is very important to find a way to alter the destiny of human failure in the context of wisdom.

Simply, the advancement of technology and even civilized human beings are not equally wise to change the course of their ignorance.

Conclusion

The wisdom of higher being and divinity can be considered as a Matrix as explained earlier (Davoudpour, 2024) of interconnected facts which are often confusing for a human mind. The Anunnaki as we generally call heavenly beings in this article, as depicted in ancient Mesopotamian mythology, represent a fascinating intersection of divine power and profound wisdom. Their influence on early human civilization and their possible connections to other mythological traditions highlight the enduring human fascination with higher beings who possess advanced knowledge. Whether viewed through the lens of mythology or speculative theories of extraterrestrial contact, the Anunnaki continue to captivate our imagination, offering insights into the nature of wisdom, divinity, and the human quest for understanding. The recurring theme of human conflict with divine beings across various mythologies underscores the complexity of the relationship between humanity

and higher powers, reflecting a universal narrative of struggle, learning, and growth.

References

1. Dalley, S. (1989). *Myths from Mesopotamia: Creation, the Flood, Gilgamesh, and Others*. Oxford University Press.
2. Davidson, H. R. E. (1990). *Gods and Myths of Northern Europe*. Penguin Books.
3. Davoudpour, A. (2024a). Religion: The Significant and Enigmatic Divine Philosophy, In the Primordial Perfection of God. *Iranian Journal of International Legal Studies*. ISSN 2957-2169
4. Davoudpour, A. (2024b). The Evolution of Consciousness: From Eden to the Suffering. *Iranian Journal of International Legal Studies*. ISSN 2957-2169.
5. Davoudpour, A. (2024c). Understanding the Matrix as the System of Divine Wisdom. *Iranian Journal of International Legal Studies*. ISSN 2957-2169.
6. George, A. (2003). *The Epic of Gilgamesh: A New Translation*. Penguin Classics.
7. Hesiod. (2006). *Theogony and Works and Days* (M. L. West, Trans.). Oxford University Press.
8. Kramer, S. N. (1963). *The Sumerians: Their History, Culture, and Character*. University of Chicago Press.
9. Pinch, G. (2004). *Egyptian Mythology: A Guide to the Gods, Goddesses, and Traditions of Ancient Egypt*. Oxford University Press.
10. Sitchin, Z. (1976). *The 12th Planet*. Harper.
11. Zimmer, H. (1951). *Myths and Symbols in Indian Art and Civilization*. Pantheon Books.